

Administrative Tasks Performance of Principals' and Teachers' job Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

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Abstract

The study investigated administrative tasks performance of principals and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 6,485 principals and teachers in 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample size of 377 principals and teachers were used for the study. The Taro Yemen Technique was used to obtain the sample size. The instruments for data collection were Administrative Tasks Performance of Principals Questionnaire and Teachers' Job Productivity Questionnaire. The face and content validity of the questionnaires were assessed by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha coefficient. The reliability index of 0.83, 0.88, 0.80, 0.81, 0.84 and 0.82 were obtained. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used in answering the research questions while the t-transformation was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of SPSS version 21.0. The study found among others that there is a very strong positive and significant relationship between principals' professional training/development programmes, principals' provision of welfare packages, participatory in decision-makings and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It was concluded that effective and efficient principals undertake several functions related to their roles in the school. One of such undertaking is their administrative tasks performance. It was recommended among others that principals should carry out professional training and the development programmes for classroom managers to be effectively skilled in instructional delivery for enhance productivity; secondary school principals should provide welfare packages such as cash gifts to encourage teachers to put in more effort in the discharge of their duties.

Keywords: Administrative Tasks performance, Participatory Decision-Making and Teachers Job Productivity

INTRODUCTION

Secondary education in Nigeria is a central mechanism that empowers young people to be skilled in order to raise the socio-economic infrastructure of the country upon graduation. The Federal Republic of Nigeria national policy on education (FRN, 2014) perceived secondary education as education given to children who has transited successfully from basic primary this level of education prepares it participant for the world of work, wealth creation and entrepreneurship. This secondary level of education is very crucial as it is expected to build the character of the learner, give the learner the right to acquire necessary skills, knowledge, attitude and values which enable them to live fruitful live and become productive citizens. The importance of secondary education can be seen from the objectives as contained in the national policy (2024) as building a firm foundation for further education and training, inculcating self-discipline and respect for the dignity of labor, developing patriotic young people equipped to contribute to social development and in the performance of their civic responsibilities, identifying individual talent and more. These stated objectives can never be actualized without secondary school teachers been motivated and committed to their duties. Therefore, secondary school principals as the leaders of the school must perform divers' administrative tasks. Igoni (2020) posited that administrative tasks performance is the skills or tools that a principal acquires and uses to influence their subordinates (teachers) for the achievement of education goals and objectives. Dornyyei (2020) described principals' administrative tasks performance as a motivational activity used by the principals to enhance their performance towards the objective of the school system. Teachers in the school need supportive practices from their school

principals to be able to perform maximally towards building or improving teachers and students performance for achievement of educational objectives.

Wey-Ameahule and Nnebue (2019) stated that this tasked could be in the area of student personal administration, instructional leadership, administration and utilization of various administrative components. The administrative tasks performance of principals is bound to affect teachers' job productivity and invariably the students' academic achievement. Akpagwu (2012) stated that these tasks could be in the area of staff and students' personnel administration, school community relation, school finance management and physical facility administration. Other administrative tasks of the principal are motivation of staff, communication, decision-making, curricular activities, conflict management, record and examination management. The principal is expected to maintain good communication, good inter-relationship with community, students and the teachers and staff welfare. In the same vein, Alugbuo in Iremeka (2021) affirmed that the administrative tasks performed by principals involve professional training/development programmes, provision of welfare packages, participatory decision-making, management of physical facilities, supportive instructional supervision and staff performance appraisal.

Ezeugbor (2015) noted that teaching is a public service that requires exceptional expertise, knowledge and specialized skills sustained through vigorous and continuous professional development. As opined by Werner and Desimone (2012) opined that professional development is a set of systematic and planned activities designed by an organization to provide its members with the opportunity to learn necessary skills to meet current and future demand. Professional development affords teachers opportunities to acquire additional competencies and qualifications to perform their teaching job successfully. It instills confidence in the teaching profession, thus, advancing teachers' career. It also empowers teachers with necessary resources required in the act of teaching and learning. When teachers receive continuous professional development, they acquire new pedagogical skills, adapt to technological advancements and improve student academic performance. It is through this programme that teachers are empowered in performing tasks of teaching effectively, produce quality outputs in teaching, solve problems and make informed choices in their job.

Furthermore, professional development will enable teachers learn new emerging technologies and become capable of adding new and relevant knowledge for the benefits of the students they are teaching. There are several professional development practices that can increase teachers' job productivity. Among others are: symposium, continuous training and re- training, workshops, research opportunity, conferences and study leaves refresher courses. Similarly, Abdulrahman (2015) pointed out that staff professional development practices through seminar, in-service training or workshop offer one of the most promising ways for improving classroom instructions.

Welfare packages involve the various services, benefits and facilities that principals offer to enrich the life of teachers for effective and efficient performance. The provision of welfare packages has been used by many organizations as a strategy of improving productivity of employees most especially when work related problems can lead to poor quality of life for employees and decline in performance (Manzini & Gwandure, 2011). In the same vein, Watitu, Kihara and Senaji (2017) pointed out that staff welfare increase the productivity of organization and promote motivation, healthy organizational relations and thereby maintaining peace in the work place. Welfare packages not measure in monetary terms alone but provision of care, gifts, display of love, appreciation, provision of safe working environment. In support of this, Lalitha and Priyanka (2014) posited that the welfare measures need not to be in monetary terms

only but in any kind/forms. Staff welfare packages in these categories involve attending to needs, ensuring interpersonal relationships, verbal praises, and letters of appreciation, recognition, offering gifts, seeing to their well-being and promoting their satisfaction on the job. Supporting this, Muruu, Were and Abok (2016) provided a list of staff welfare as: principals' provision of merits awards, equipping staff offices, recognition of outstanding staff and opportunity for in-service training. The provision of welfare packages determines the level of teachers' productivity.

The word "decision-making" has been defined in varied perspectives by various authors. Igwe in Okoroma (2019) perceived decision making as a purposive act intended to achieve desired outcome which is usually envisaged by the decision-maker. Mcammy in Okoroma (2019) defined decision-making as the process of administration. Chike-Okoli (2019) posited that decision-making is a major responsibility of all administrators. It is the process of choosing from among alternative courses of action. It is also the process by which decisions are not only arrived at but implemented.

The importance of decision-making is enormous both on the organizational management point of view and the work life of the subordinates towards the achievement of the organizational goals. Osuji (2010) stated that when policies and plans have been discussed and agreed upon, it is easier to carry staff in implementing them. The involvement of teachers in decision-making becomes imperative following the increase in teachers' awareness of the impact their participation has on the implementation of such decisions. Individual members' feelings of self-realization are related to participation in decision making and its consequences. It can be rightly argued that participation in decision-making contributes to the general well-being of teachers. It is obvious that the school principal is the driver of the teachers' productivity.

Productivity is the rate at which a worker, a company or a country produces goods, and the amount produced, compared with how much time, work and money is needed to produce them (Hornby, 2010). Productivity deals with a measure of performance that indicates how many inputs it takes to produce or create an output. Thus, productivity is outputs divided by inputs. Thus, the fewer inputs it takes to produce an output, the higher the productivity. In education, inputs + process = Output. When the inputs and the process are in order, the right output (productivity) will emerge (Oluwuo & Agabi, 2014). According to Oluwuo and Agabi (2014), the inputs deal with the teacher, his qualification, experience, text in use, syllabus, scheme of work, lesson notes, time of allotment, books on the subject, instructional materials, school facilities, nature of students admitted, etc. The process deals with teacher demeanor, pupil written work; assignments and corrections, continuous assessment, method of teaching and general delivery process. The output (productivity) deals with standard of subject at certificate examination, quality of product. Oluwuo and Agabi (2014) revealed that teachers' productivity is measured by the following: Students' performance on standard achievement tests as well as students' performance on minimum competency tests, number of students who go to post-secondary education or those who get employed, daily student and teacher attendance rates, rates of suspensions and other exclusion, students' awards in academic or vocational competition, awards for outstanding school programmes, quality of students' performance in programmes such as arts, music and drama.

In the light of the above fact therefore, the teachers' productivity relates to his job. The teachers' job is basically to teach learners, using relevant resources, appropriate language and many other appropriate

media to ensure that learning takes place within the time schedule of any given lesson. The teachers' job also includes identifying and giving closer attention to learners who are slower at learning than the rest of the class. This enables weak or slow learners catch up with their contemporaries in the class (Agabi, 2018). At the pre-primary and lower basic classes, the teacher may go as far as holding the hand of a learner to guide the learner in writing and in the making of shapes. This personal attention helps to sustain the interest of the learner in the learning process and in classroom educational activities. This personal attention given to weak learners is, as observed by Akubue in Agabi (2018), a strong motivating factor for the sustenance of interest in learning because no child likes to be left behind in group efforts at success. It is the job of the teacher to ensure that none is left behind in the course of teaching and in the achievement of learning. Teachers' job productivity is the extent a teacher is able to deliver his roles and responsibility to the school and the learners. In education, productivity is the rate at which educational objectives are achieved; it is a continuous process, taking into consideration the input, process and output phases of education (Yusuf, 2017). Wood (2015) described productivity as the accomplishment of specific tasks in relation to present standards that indicates the accuracy, cost, speed and completeness in a manner that weakens attainment of a predetermined goal in the school.

Teachers' job productivity is the ability of teachers to effectively and efficiently carry out adequate lesson preparation, professionalism, classroom management and control, discipline, adequate school climate, record keeping, and evaluation of students' work. Cook (2008) averred that job productivity of teachers is considered as the teachers' observable behaviors related to outcomes which are relevant to educational goals. Teachers' productivity in education relates essentially to issues that concerns delivery of educational outcomes which meet the needs and expectations of the society in an efficient, accountable and cost effective way, pursuit of excellence in both academic and other areas of education, participation of teacher educators in choosing the best teaching and learning strategies that suit the needs of the teachers and student of a particular school, and provision of educational diversity and choice to parents and students.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigeria secondary school prepares students for self-improvement and achievement of excellence. Recently, it has been observed that teachers now indulge in selling of cosmetics, handbags and others items within the school premises to make ends means (Ogona 2021). The researcher also observed that there is declining interest of students towards schooling and reported poor performance of students in internal and external examination and other unreasonable behavior by teachers such as absenteeism, persistent lateness to school, neglect and other forms of indiscipline in the study area, which could be attributed to low students' achievement. This buttered the researcher could these be that teachers are not well paid? Or secondary school principals, not applying motivational activities while performing their duties in order to propel teachers to put in their best for the achievement of education goals and objectives. These led the researcher to examine the relationship between administrative tasks performance of principals and student job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between administrative tasks performance of principals and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in River State. Specifically, the study addresses the following:

1. Find out the relationship between principals' professional training/development programmes and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

2. Examine the relationship between principals' provision of welfare packages and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. Identify the relationship between principals' participatory decision-making and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between principals' professional training/development programmes and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' provision of welfare packages and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between principals' participatory decision-making and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of the significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' professional training/developments programmes and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' provision of welfare packages and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between principals' participatory decision-making and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised of 6,485 principals and teachers (311 principals and 6,174 teachers) in all the 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Taro Yemen formula was used to obtain the sample size of 377 respondent (77 principals and 300 teachers). While stratified random sampling techniques was adopted in selecting the sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was two separate instruments titled: "Administrative Tasks Performance of Principals' Questionnaire (ATPPQ)" the second instrument assessed "Teachers' Job Productivity Questionnaire (TJPQ)" designed by the researcher in the modified 4point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 point, Disagree (D) = 2 point, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1point. The instrument was face and content validated by three experts in the Department of Educational Management, Measurements and Evaluations. Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to determine and obtain reliability indexes of 0.83, 0.83, 0.88, 0.80, 0.81, 0.84 and 0.82. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to answer the stated research question while the null hypotheses were test using t-transformation statistic at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between principals’ professional training/development programmes and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Analysis of Principals’ Professional Training/ Development Programmes and Teachers’ Job Productivity

		Principals’ Professional Training/ Development Programmes	Teachers’ Job Productivity
Principals’ Professional Training/ Development Programmes	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.844**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	N	370	370
Teachers’ Job Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.844**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	370	370

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025.

Table 1 above shows the answer to research question one posed to examine the relationship between principals’ professional training/development programmes and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. As revealed by the table, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) of 0.844 which is positive and greater than 0.5 indicates that there is a very strong positive relationship between principals’ professional training/development programmes and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The implication of this is that increase in principals’ professional training/development programmes would lead to an increase in teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between principals’ provision of welfare packages and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Analysis of Principals’ Provision of Welfare Packages and Teachers’ Job Productivity

		Principals’ Provision of Welfare Packages	Teachers’ Job Productivity
Principals’ Provision of Welfare Packages	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.837**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	N	370	370
Teachers’ Job Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.837**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	370	370

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025.

Table 2 above shows the result of the answer to the second research question raised to examine the relationship between principals’ provision of welfare packages and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. As revealed by the table, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) of 0.837 which is positive and greater than 0.5 indicates that there is a very strong positive relationship between principals’ provision of welfare packages and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The implication of this is that increase in principals’ provision of welfare packages would lead to an increase in teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between principals’ participatory decision-making and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) Analysis of Principals’ Participatory Decision-Making and Teachers’ Job Productivity

		Principals’ Participatory Decision- Making	Teachers’ Job Productivity
Principals’ Participatory Decision-Making	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	N	370	370
Teachers’ Job Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.579**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	370	370

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025.

Table 3 above shows the answer to the third research question posed to examine the relationship between principals’ participatory decision-making and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. As revealed by the table, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) of 0.579 which is positive and greater than 0.5 indicates that there is a very moderate positive relationship between principals’ participatory decision-making and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The implication of this is that increase in principals’ participatory decision-making would lead to an increase in teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between principals’ professional training/ development programmes and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: T-Transformation Analysis of Principals’ Professional Training/ Development Programmes and Teachers’ Job Productivity

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.645	.126		5.125	.000
1 Principals’ Professional Training/ Development Programmes	1.098	.029	.892	3.358	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers’ Job Productivity

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4 above shows the result of hypothesis one tested. As revealed by the table, the coefficient of 1.098 indicates that there is a positive relationship between principals’ professional training/development programmes and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Since the significant value (P-value) of 0.000 is less than 0.05, the researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis. The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between principals’ professional training/development programmes and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between principals’ provision of welfare packages and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: T-Transformation Analysis of Principals’ Provision of Welfare Packages and Teachers’ Job Productivity

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.842	.087		9.652	.000
1 Principals’ Provision of Welfare Packages	.818	.021	.899	38.952	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers’ Job Productivity

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4: above shows the result of hypothesis two tested. As revealed by the table, the coefficient of 0.818 indicates that there is a positive relationship between principals’ provision of welfare packages and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Since the significant value (P-value) of 0.000 is less than 0.05, the researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis. The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between principals’ provision of welfare packages and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between principals’ participatory decision-making and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: T-Transformation Analysis of Principals’ Participatory Decision-Making and Teachers’ Job Productivity

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.247	.042		5.929	.000
1 Principals’ Participatory Decision-Making	.924	.013	.973	70.256	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers’ Job Productivity

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2025.

Table 6 above shows the result of hypothesis three tested. As revealed by the table, the coefficient of 0.924 indicates that there is a positive relationship between principals’ participatory decision-making and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Since the significant value (P-value) of 0.000 is less than 0.05, the researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis. The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between principals’ participatory decision-making and teachers’ job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on research question 1 revealed that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) of 0.844 which is positive and greater than 0.5 indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between principals' professional training/development programmes and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This result aligns with the views of Emechebe (2009) that in educational institutions, there is need to design training and development programmes for newly employed staff. This will help to improve their standard of productivity and enhance the standard of education in the country. Obasi and Asodike (2007) affirmed that in schools teachers are given the opportunity to improve skills and competences through regular participation in workshops and seminars. They are encouraged to undertake in-service training programmes such as sandwich programmes organized by universities during the long vacations for staff development. When teachers are properly trained, they get more developed through competence exposure to impact better on the students and get them equally exposed and more knowledgeable.

The findings corroborate the views of Althassan (2014) who argued that professional development programmes have been one of the major administrative tasks performed by principals to develop their teachers. The principals have the responsibility to perform their administrative tasks in the area of training and retraining of teachers so as to enable them discharge their instructional delivery tasks in a professional manner. Rolfe (2007) stated that the exposure of teachers to workshop training greatly influence lesson output. Frequently exposure of teachers to workshop training makes the teacher highly competent to evaluate his/her academic progress.

Findings on research question 2 revealed that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) of 0.837 which is positive and greater than 0.5 indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between principals' provision of welfare packages and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This result agrees with the assertions of Arikewuyo and Adegbesan (2009) that various studies have shown that staff that are taken care of or motivated could be highly productive. Manzini and Gwandure (2011) averred that the provision of welfare packages has been used by many organizations as a strategy of improving productivity of employees most especially when work related problems can lead to poor quality of life for employees and decline in performance. In the same vein, Watitu, Kihara and Senaji (2017) pointed out that staff welfare increase the productivity of organization and promote motivation, healthy organizational relations and thereby maintain peace in the work place.

The finding further corroborates the views of Ratro (2015) that the ability of employers to offer extra incentives in the form of employees' welfare scheme makes employees to be enthusiastic and more dedicated to their work. Gupta (2014) averred that employee welfare packages/programmes increase industrial efficiency which benefits both management and employers. Jepkemoi in Manafa (2020) opined that the provision of wellbeing to teachers is a source of earning and satisfaction which is likely to increase their productivity because they are motivated and happy. Money in Imo (2013) stated that the provision of welfare packages determine the level of teachers' productivity. Other studies and researchers have proven that when teachers are highly motivated or encouraged through giving of gifts or other welfare packages it helps in encouraging them in giving out their best (Lim, 2013).

Findings on research question 3 revealed that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) of 0.579 which is positive and greater than 0.5 indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between principals' participatory decision-making and teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This result aligns with the views of Nwadiani (2008) that the principal is the fulcrum upon which the success or failure of school administration revolves around, noting that the principals must maintain close ties with his teaches in the achievement of school goals. The attainment of the school goals possibly depends on principals' decision making strategies. Similarly, Igwe in Okoroma (2019) asserted that all other administrative activities or functions are dependent upon administrative decisions.

Corroborating the above finding, Alkin (2015) stated that involving teachers in taking decisions in issues that affected their welfare in schools remains not only an important strategy but also a vital administrative task that ensures increased teachers' job productivity. Kukenberger (2015) supported that when employees have the ability to participate in decision making, they perceive it as an organizational support that may facilitate group commitment. Nicholls (2021) affirmed that involving teachers in decision making represents a useful strategy by the principals to make proper use of the teachers' creative abilities and initiatives to increase their recognition in the performance of their duties. In the same vein, Mullins (2014) opined that staff participating in decision making leads to higher performance. Obi in Igbaseimokumo (2019) discovered that teachers' involvement in decision making in their schools enhanced their job performance.

CONCLUSION

Effective and efficient principals undertake several functions related to their roles in the school. One of such undertaking is their administrative tasks performance. Administrative tasks performance of secondary school principals such as professional training/development programmes, provision of welfare packages, and participatory decision-making, have very strong positive and significant relationship with teachers' job productivity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals should carry out professional training and development programmes for classroom managers to be effectively skilled in instructional delivery for enhanced productivity.
2. Secondary school principals should provide welfare packages either monetary or non-monetary reward to encourage teachers to put in more effort in the discharge of their duties.
3. Secondary school managers should practice participatory decision-making by involving teachers in discussions concerning school plans and policies for effective implementation.

References

- Abdulkareem, A. Y., & Fasasi, Y. A. (2015). *Management of educational facilities in Nigeria Secondary Schools: The roles of administrators and inspectors*. Ilorin: Department of Education Management.
- Adikom, I. N., & Oluwuo, S. O. (2015). Assessment of physical facilities and staffing specification in the implementation of early childhood education in public school in Rivers State. *African Journal of Education Research and Development (AJERD)*, 8(1), 210-218.
- Agabi, C. O. (2016). *Resourcing for effective learning in schools*. Germany: Lap Lambert.

- Agabi, C. O. (2018). The supply of teachers in public schools. In N. P. Ololube (Ed). *Handbook of Research on Educational Planning and Policy Analysis* (156-169). Port Harcourt: Pearl Publishers.
- Agabi, C. O. Onyeike, V. C., & Wali, W. I. (2013). *Classroom management: A practical approach*. Port Harcourt: University of Port Harcourt Press.
- Akpagwu, S. O. (2012). *Educational management: Theory and practice*. Markudi: Destiny Ventures.
- Arikewuyo, M. O., & Adegbesan, S. O. (2009). Practicum on administration of personnel in education. In J. B. Babalola, & A. O. Ayeni (Eds). *Educational Management: Theories and Tasks* (323-337). Ibadan: Macmillan Publishers.
- Chike-Okoli, A. (2009). Decision-making management in education. In J. B. Babalola, & A. O. Ayeru (Eds). *Educational Management: Theories and Tasks* (519-532). Lagos: Macmillan Publishers.
- Dienye, N, E., & Dienye, V. U. (2006). The secondary school principal as a leader and change
- Donnelly, J. H. (2002). Fundamentals of management (8th Edition). *Journal*, 6(7/8), 117-122.
- Donnelly, G., M. (1995). *Fundamentals of management*, (6th edition). United State America: Von Hoffman Press.
- .Emechebe, S. N. (2009). Human resource management in education. In J. B. Babalola, & A. O. Ayeni (Eds). *Educational Management: Theories and Tasks* (629-645). Ibadan: Macmillan Publishers.
- .Mangini, H., & Gwandure, C. (2011). *The provision of employee assistance programme in South Africa football clubs*. South Africa: University of Witwatersrand.
- Nwadani, C. (2008). Problems of quality in secondary education. *Journal of Educational Management*, 5, 120-128.
- Odeku, O. F., & Odeku, K. O. (2014). In pursuit of the employees' welfare in the workplace: Issue in perspectives. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 5(15) 652-660.
- Ogunsaju, S. (2010). Nature and purpose of education management. In D.O. Durosaro, & S. Ogunsaju (Eds). *The Craft of Educational Management* (172-185). Ibadan: Haytee Books.
- Okoroma, N. S. (2009). *Educational management, planning and policy: A broad perspective*. Port Harcourt: University of Port Harcourt Press.
- Okoroma, N. S. (2016). *Perspective of educational management, planning and policy analysis*. Port Harcourt: Modern Skills Productions.
- Oluwuo, S. O., & Agabi, E. (2014). Supervision and teacher productivity at primary and secondary school levels in Rivers State. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development (AJERD)*, 7(V1), 52-58.
- Osuji W. A. (2009). Administrative decision making in secondary schools in Abia and Umuahia Education Zone: Extent of teachers' participation. *Unpublished Masters Dissertation*. Imo State University.

- Osuji, C. U., & Koko, M. N. (2016). Teachers' participation in decision-making for sustainable development: A case of Rivers State secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research*, 3(6), 21-27.
- Wey-Amaehule, B. Ikogi R.J. (2021) Assessment of Utilization of modern technology in management of tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State (Education Lectureres Perspective) *British Journal of Education* 9 (10), 14-50
- Wey-Amaehule, B. Omoregbe S.O. (2025) influence of social networking tools on lecturers' effective instructional delivery in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, *Journal of Education* 24 (2), 1-3
- Wey-Amaehule, B. & Nnebue, A.H. (2019). Status of school plant maintainace among public secondary school principals in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 7 (1), 49-56.